

Polarographic Study of the β -Mercapto-propionic Acid Complexes of Cadmium

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The complexation of cadmium by β -Mercapto propionic acid has been studied polarographically. The reduction of Cd^{2+} in mercapto-propionate solution has been found to be reversible involving two electron transfer process. The half-wave potential shifts to more negative value with the increase in ligand concentration indicating the complexation. The potential vs concentration data at unit ionic strength ($\mu = 1$) were interpreted on the basis of the formation of four complex species CdA , CdA_2^{2-} , CdA_3^{4-} , and CdA_4^{6-} employing De Ford and Hume's method. The logarithms of the stability constants at 30° were found to be $\log K_1 = 2.0$, $\log K_2 = 3.60$, $\log K_3 = 4.84$ and $\log K_4 = 6.55$ respectively.

β -Mercapto-propionic acid (H_2A), which figures prominently in the discussion of sulphur containing ligands and provides two possible coordination sites *viz.*, $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{SH}$ groups, has been reported to form complexes with Co(III) ⁽¹⁾, La ⁽²⁾, Ce ⁽²⁾ etc. Recently, it has also been used as an analytical reagent for the detection and determination of Pd^{2+} ⁽³⁾, Co^{2+} ⁽⁴⁾ etc. As a part of our investigations of a series of the complexes of β -mercapto propionic acid with various metals such as Zn^{2+} ⁽⁵⁾, Ni^{2+} ⁽⁶⁾, Tl(I) ⁽⁷⁾ etc., the Cd-mercapto with various metals propionate system has been studied polarographically to determine the stability constants of the complex ions formed. There is, however, no reference in the literature regarding the polarographic study of Cadmium-mercapto-propionate system.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -Mercapto propionic acid (99.1% Evan's Chemetics, Inc., N.Y.) as its sodium salt was used as a complexing agent. All other chemicals were reagent grade and used without purification. Stock solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air free conductivity water. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used as maximum suppressor. Cadmium contents in Cadmium sulphate solutions were checked by estimating it as cadmium oxinate.

Polarographic curves were recorded manually by a Cambridge (General purpose) Polarograph using a thermostated H-Cell. An external saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar bridge served as a reference electrode. The capillary characteristics measured in $1.0M$ KNO_3 at $E_{d.e.} = -1.0$ volt and at a mercury height of 65.0 cm. were $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.801 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$.

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Dissolved air was removed from the solution by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen through the cell and passing it over the solution during the measurements. Necessary corrections for iR drop and residual current were applied in determining half-wave potentials and diffusion current data respectively.

For complexation studies, a series of 1.0 *mM* CdSO_4 solutions containing varying concentrations ($2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-1}M$) of sodium mercapto-propionate and 0.002% Triton X-100 were prepared. Requisite amounts of KCl were added to maintain the ionic strength at 1.0*M*. Thoroughly mixed solutions were transferred to cell and polarograms recorded. Half-wave potentials were obtained from the plots of $E_{d.e}$ vs $\log i/id-i$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All the plots of $\log i/id-i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$, (corresponding to the $c-v$ curves of Cd^{2+} in different concentrations of sodium-mercapto propionate) yielded straight lines with slopes which agreed with theoretical value, the mean slope for the series was 0.0325, showing the reversibility of the reduction. The half-wave potentials evaluated from the log plots for the current voltage curves of Cd^{2+} in varying ligand concentrations and corresponding diffusion current values have been recorded in Table I. The appreciable difference in the diffusion currents

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Cx moles/lit.	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_a	$F_0(x)$ $\times 10^2$	$F_1(x)$ $\times 10^3$	$F_2(x)$ $\times 10^4$	$F_3(x)$ $\times 10^5$	$F_4(x)$ $\times 10^6$
1	0.0	0.644	7.35	—	—	—	—	—
2	0.02	0.661	4.82	0.057	0.2367	0.6837	1.4187	3.593
3	0.04	0.673	3.65	0.1929	0.4572	0.8831	1.2078	1.2695
4	0.06	0.683	2.61	0.5883	0.9805	1.467	1.779	1.798
5	0.08	0.695	1.81	2.16	2.687	3.233	3.542	3.552
6	0.10	0.700	1.31	4.721	4.711	4.611	4.211	3.511

of the Cd^{2+} ion alone and in the presence of ligand indicates that the aqueo cadmium ion and Cd-mercapto propionate complex differ in size. The half wave potentials were found to shift towards more negative values with increasing ligand concentration showing the complex formation.

A plot of $E_{1/2}$ as a function of $\log [\text{Mercapto-propionate}]$ showed curvature expected from the formation of successive complexes (Fig. 1). If single strong complexes are involved, a simple plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{ligand}]$ gives sufficient information for the elucidation of the complex. With successive complexes more elaborate calculations are required. De Ford and Hume⁽⁸⁾ have derived a series of equations to relate polarographic data to complexity

constants. For the reversible polarographic reduction of a complexed metal on to the metal amalgam

they have defined functions, $F_j(X)$ such that

$$F_0(x) = \text{antilog} \left\{ 0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} \times \left[(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c \right] + \log \frac{I_s}{I_c} \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$F_1(x) = [F_0(x) - (K_0/f_s)]/C_x f_x \quad (3)$$

$$F_2(x) = [F_1(x) - K_1/f_{m_x}]/C_x f_x, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ are the half wave potentials for the uncomplexed and complexed metal ions respectively; and I_s and I_c are the experimentally determined diffusion currents for these species. K_0 , the formation constant of zero complex, is defined as unity. f_s and f_x are the activity coefficients of uncomplexed metal ion and the complexing ligand respectively and C_x is the concentration of ligand, K_1 is the formation constant of 1 : 1 complex and f_{m_x} the activity coefficient of the complex.

The intercept, of a plot of $F_j(X)$ vs $C_x f_x$, extrapolated to $C_x = 0$, is equal to K_j/f_{m_x} . Since the ionic strength is maintained constant throughout the series of measurements, the ionic atmosphere and hence the several activity coefficients probably change very little and one may equate them to unity⁽⁹⁾.

Fig. 1. Plot of $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs. $\log C_x$

Figure 2 shows the plots of $F_0(x)$ and $F_1(x)$ and Fig. 3, the plots of $F_2(x)$, $F_3(x)$ and $F_4(x)$ vs. ligand concentration. Extrapolation of these curves at $C_x f_x = 0$, gave values for the four stability constants as follows :

$$K_1 = 1.0 \times 10^2; \quad K_2 = 4.0 \times 10^3, \quad K_3 = 7.0 \times 10^4 \quad \text{and} \quad K_4 = 3.59 \times 10^6.$$

The plot of $F_4(x)$ (Fig. 3) showed a horizontal line and indicated that only four complexes were involved. As a check on the values for K_2 , K_3 and K_4 , the limiting slopes were

obtained which approximate the K values for the next higher complex⁽⁸⁾. The limiting slope for the $F_1(x)$ curve was calculated as 3.80×10^3 ($K_2 = 4.0 \times 10^3$) that for $F_2(x)$ curve as 7.90×10^4 ($K_3 = 7.0 \times 10^4$) and for $F_3(x)$ curve as 3.50×10^6 ($K_4 = 3.59 \times 10^6$).

Fig. 2. Values of $F_0(x)$ and $F_1(x)$.

The present investigation reveals (i) the formation of four complexes CdA , CdA_2^{2-} , CdA_3^{4-} and CdA_4^{6-} of Cd^{2+} with mercapto propionate ion, ii) the $\log K$ values were found to be $\log K_1 = 2.0$, $\log K_2 = 3.60$, $\log K_3 = 4.84$ and $\log K_4 = 6.55$ respectively.

Fig. 3. Values of $F_2(x)$, $F_3(x)$ and $F_4(x)$.

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